

Bagua: An Ancient Structural Framework for Classification and Analysis with Analogies to the Modern 2×2 Contingency Table

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Abstract

This study systematically examines the structure of the Bagua from the I Ching (hereafter “Bagua”) from a data-analytical perspective. It is shown that the millennia-old Bagua can be understood as a method of data analysis that structurally corresponds to the 2×2 contingency table, yet existed several thousand years before the development of percentage calculation.

Over the course of historical development, however, interpretations—among them those influenced by Confucius—came to dominate and interpreted the Bagua primarily from a philosophical or symbolic perspective. In this process, a possible analytical approach was lost over centuries, so that in contemporary perception the Bagua is often understood only as a mystical element. In the present work, the Bagua is interpreted by us as a combinatorial structure consisting of three binary levels and is reanalyzed with regard to its structural as well as data-related relationships.

It is further shown that although the Bagua formally exhibits binary characteristics, as already described by Leibniz, its structure is better understood as a system based on complement relations and not as a simple binary encoding. In this respect, it shows a greater proximity to the fundamental concepts of set theory developed in 19th-century Europe, although the origins of the Bagua date back several thousand years.

On the basis of a structured analysis of a concrete example (the “Steve problem” formulated by Kahneman), as well as in comparison with the 2×2 contingency table, it is further shown that the Bagua is capable of representing symmetric relationships and direct comparisons within the same level, whereas the 2×2 contingency table is particularly suited to representing conditional dependencies between variables and proportional relationships. Both forms of representation therefore fulfill different but complementary functions.

Building on this, it is proposed that the Bagua can be understood as an early instrument of data classification and analysis whose functioning does not depend on percentage calculation. Furthermore, in connection with the structural analysis of He Tu and Luo Shu, the possibility is discussed that point-based markings can be interpreted as a means of data representation.

In summary, a structural approach to understanding the Bagua is proposed, which considers it as a potential framework for the representation and analysis of data. This perspective contributes to making the internal relationships of traditional diagrammatic forms visible and at the same time provides a new interpretative framework together with a directly applicable analytical approach.

1. Introduction

The Bagua from the I Ching (hereafter “Bagua”) originates in ancient China and can be historically traced back several thousand years, possibly even further. Archaeological evidence suggests that this system of symbols likely emerged prior to the development of fully developed writing systems. Therefore, the origins of the Bagua as well as its early modes of application have long been among the central questions of research.

Although traditional approaches largely follow an interpretative tradition shaped by Confucius (551–479 BCE) and primarily interpret the Bagua from a philosophical or symbolic perspective, a pronounced tendency toward mystification can be observed in the present, while it is also frequently applied in practical contexts such as Feng Shui (Wilhelm, 1967). Nevertheless, according to the current state of the literature, a systematic analysis of the underlying structure of the Bagua as well as its original function is still lacking.

Against this background, the present study pursues an alternative approach by reexamining the Bagua from a structural and data-analytical perspective and analyzing its possible functions in the context of the representation and processing of information. It is argued that the Bagua can originally be understood as an early form of data analysis, whose original meaning has been increasingly weakened and ultimately lost over the course of historical development.

2. Structure and Combinatorial Properties of the Bagua

Although the Bagua diagram formally appears as a three-level system of binary elements, the present work takes the view that its internal structure should rather be understood as a system based on complement relations and not as a simple binary encoding as interpreted by Leibniz (Leibniz, 1703); in this respect, it shows a closer affinity to the fundamental concepts of set theory developed in 19th-century Europe (Halmos, 1960; Cantor, 1895).

As shown in Figure 1, each trigram consists of three horizontal lines arranged from bottom to top. A continuous line represents a Yang element, whereas a broken line represents a Yin element. These three lines are referred to as the first, second, and third Yao (first, second, and third levels).

Figure 1. Structure of the Bagua system: representation of Yin and Yang lines, the three Yao levels, and the eight trigrams in the early-heaven Bagua diagram.

From a structural perspective, this results in a three-level binary system. Since each level can assume two possible states (Yin or Yang), a total of $2^3 = 8$ different combinations arise, corresponding to the eight fundamental trigrams (Gua): Qian, Dui, Li, Zhen, Xun, Kan, Gen, and Kun.

If these eight trigrams are arranged in a specific order and connected cyclically, the complete Bagua diagram emerges (Fig. 1, bottom right). In this work, the early-heaven Bagua diagram is used; the reasons for this are explained in Chapter 4.

To illustrate the structure and its possible application, an example is introduced based on the “Steve problem” formulated by Kahneman (Kahneman, 2011). It is assumed that in a village there exist only two occupational groups: farmers and librarians. Steve is described as a person who wears glasses and appears rather reserved. The central question is: to which of the two occupational groups does Steve belong with higher probability, given that he wears glasses?

Figure 2. Structural representation of the “Steve problem” using the Bagua diagram.

As shown in Figure 2, an attempt is made to represent this problem in a structured form using the Bagua diagram. Specifically, the three horizontal lines are assigned to different variables from bottom to top: the lowest level represents the occupational category, namely either farmer or librarian; the middle level describes an individual characteristic, namely the wearing of glasses (where “strong arms” is used as a contrasting characteristic for not wearing glasses); the top level indicates whether one of the four possible state combinations resulting from the lower two levels is present.

This form of representation may appear somewhat complex at first. As an example, the two markings in the center of the figure may be considered: the combination marked with a checkmark denotes “not a farmer with glasses.” It should be noted that “not a farmer with glasses” here does not merely refer to “a farmer without glasses,” but rather represents a broader set that includes both farmers without glasses and all librarians (regardless of whether they wear glasses or not).

From the perspective of set theory, this form of representation corresponds to the definition of the complement of a given category within a universal set. In this context, the present work proposes for the first time a systematic interpretation of the Bagua structure on the basis of complement relations. The reasons why this interpretation is of central importance and why, from our perspective, it is also highly likely to correspond to its original use will be explained in the following.

3. Exemplary Application and Structural Comparison

For further clarification, a numerical example is considered. Four observers each collect data from a sample of 100 villagers, whereby each observer records only one specific combined

category. The data collection thus does not proceed step by step according to individual attributes, but directly for combined states.

For example, the first observer records exclusively “farmers with glasses” and counts 15 corresponding cases, while the remaining 85 cases do not belong to this category. A fourth observer records “librarians without glasses” and finds 10 corresponding cases.

Figure 3. Example data for the “Steve problem.”

When these data are transferred into the Bagua structure (Fig. 3), direct comparisons between categories can be carried out. Under the condition “glasses,” for example, a ratio of 15 farmers to 5 librarians is obtained, from which it follows that Steve is more likely to be a farmer.

Figure 4. Initial structural comparison between the Bagua diagram and the 2×2 contingency table.

For better clarity, in Figure 4 the Bagua diagram is subdivided into sections and marked by triangular shapes. It should be noted that, in the structural interpretation of the Bagua, the three lines are read from the inside to the outside, that is, step by step from bottom to top.

In addition, a simplification of the data shown in Figure 3 is carried out: the data marked in red are removed, so that only the values shown in black remain. These four data groups are then transferred into the 2×2 contingency table shown on the right.

Through this comparison, it can be observed that the Bagua diagram exhibits several structural similarities to the 2×2 contingency table. The same information can also be read from the 2×2 contingency table, namely that under the condition that Steve wears glasses, the probability that he is a farmer (value: 15) is higher than the probability that he is a librarian (value: 5).

4. Comparison between the Bagua Diagram and the 2×2 contingency table and Its “Yi” Property

Here, “Yi” (易) refers to a central concept of the I Ching, whose meaning will be clarified in the following.

In Figure 5, a further structural comparison between the Bagua representation and the 2×2 contingency table is carried out. In the Bagua diagram (left representation), the central feature consists in the direct representation of the relationships between the nodes of the third level. This third level can be understood as the finest unit of data, which is determined by the combination of three binary attributes. For example, attributes such as “farmer/librarian” and “glasses/no glasses” jointly define a specific node.

Within this structure, comparisons primarily manifest as horizontal relationships within the same level (intra-layer). Thus, under the condition “glasses,” a ratio of 15 to 5 between farmers and librarians arises. In addition, within a single node, the relations between the “fulfillment of the condition” and its complement can also be considered, for example in the ratio of 15 to 85.

Furthermore, the Bagua structure exhibits an inherent symmetry, through which corresponding relations can be directly read. For example, the ratio between “farmers without glasses” and “librarians without glasses” is 70:10.

This shows that the Bagua diagram structurally already encodes equivalence comparisons as well as complement and symmetry mappings intrinsically.

Figure 5. Further structural comparison between the Bagua diagram and the 2x2 contingency table.

In contrast, the 2x2 contingency table on the right is particularly suitable for representing relationships between different levels (inter-layer) (Gigerenzer & Hoffrage, 1995). In this representation, data are organized as the joint distribution of two binary variables, which allows conditional probabilities and marginal distributions to be directly calculated.

For example, within a column, a ratio of 15 to 70 arises between “farmers with glasses” and “farmers without glasses”; correspondingly, the ratio for librarians is 5 to 10. Through normalization along rows or columns, conditional proportions can also be directly determined, for instance a ratio of 15 to 85 for “farmers with glasses” relative to the total number of farmers, which corresponds to a typical conditional probability.

From this it follows that the two forms of representation fulfill different structural functions:

- the Bagua diagram emphasizes symmetric relationships and direct comparisons within the same level;
- the 2x2 contingency table, by contrast, focuses on conditional dependencies between variables as well as on proportional calculations;
- in essence, however, the Bagua corresponds to the 2x2 contingency table prior to the development of percentage calculation.

Figure 6. The “Yi” property of the Bagua diagram.

In Figure 6, the structural relationship between neighboring trigrams in the Bagua diagram is further examined. It can be observed that all neighboring trigrams follow a principle of minimal change (minimal change principle). This minimal change manifests itself in two fundamental forms:

- one line changes its state from continuous (Yang) to broken (Yin), or vice versa;
- two lines exchange their positions, for example from “top broken, bottom continuous” to “top continuous, bottom broken.”

In other words, the transition from one trigram to a neighboring one requires only the modification of a single structural element or a minimal local rearrangement.

This observation can be related to the different meanings of the term “Yi” in the *I Ching*. Traditionally, “Yi” comprises two central aspects: on the one hand, “simplicity” (簡易), that is, the reduction to fundamental structures and rules; on the other hand, “change” (變易), that is, the continuous transformation of states. Taken together, this results in the principle of “simple change,” in which complex developments arise from minimal, local modifications. In the early-heaven Bagua diagram, this principle becomes clearly visible: the relationship between neighboring trigrams can in each case be reduced to a single minimal structural change.

From a combinatorial perspective, the arrangement of the eight trigrams can be understood as a permutation problem on a cyclic structure (permutations on a cycle). Due to rotational symmetry, different starting points correspond merely to cyclic shifts (cyclic equivalence) and therefore do not represent structurally distinct configurations. After eliminating this rotational symmetry, the number of independent arrangements is $7! = 5040$.

If reflection symmetry is additionally taken into account, the number of independent configurations is further reduced to $7!/2 = 2520$.

A comparison of different Bagua arrangements shows that the early-heaven Bagua diagram occupies a special structural position, as it simultaneously satisfies two central properties.

First, it corresponds to the fundamental principle of change of “Yi,” that is, the principle of minimal local change (minimal local change principle). In this structure, transitions between neighboring trigrams occur exclusively through minimal adjustments of individual lines, thereby ensuring the continuity and simplicity of the transformation process.

Second, the overall structure exhibits a natural correspondence to the binary classification structure of the 2×2 contingency table. Through global symmetry, relationships between categories can be clearly represented and analyzed, so that the structure can be interpreted as a suitable means for the representation of data.

Figure 7. Early-heaven and later-heaven Bagua diagrams.

In contrast, the later-heaven Bagua diagram, which has been frequently used in traditional literature since Confucius (cf. Fig. 7), does not satisfy these two properties: on the one hand, neighboring trigrams do not strictly follow the principle of minimal change; on the other hand, its overall structure cannot be directly mapped onto the binary classification of the 2×2 contingency table. Therefore, the later-heaven Bagua diagram does not possess a corresponding suitability for data-analytical applications.

A structural comparison thus shows that the original early-heaven Bagua diagram is the only arrangement that simultaneously satisfies both properties:

- the adherence to the principle of minimal local change between neighboring trigrams;
- a global structure that is compatible with the binary classification of the 2×2 contingency table.

To explain this uniqueness, the arrangement is first considered under the restriction to only two levels (first and second line). Under the assumption of the minimal change principle and after eliminating rotational symmetry, it is shown that only a single valid arrangement exists.

When the third level is subsequently included, the state space is expanded; however, under the same structural conditions, the number of valid arrangements remains one. This uniquely determined structure corresponds to the early-heaven Bagua diagram alone.

5. Possible Application Scenarios and Historical Interpretation

To account for more realistic conditions, a further example of data collection is constructed (cf. Fig. 8). In contrast to the previously considered situation, it is no longer assumed that all observers record the same number of individuals. Instead, they are allowed to freely choose the sample size according to the respective situation, resulting in a scenario with unequal sample sizes.

Specifically, four observers are defined, each recording different combinations of attributes:

- The first observer focuses on “farmers with glasses.” Among the 10 observed villagers, 3 satisfy this attribute, while 7 do not belong to this category.
- The second observer records “farmers without glasses.” Of the 5 observed individuals, 2 satisfy this condition, while 3 do not belong to this category.
- The third observer examines “librarians with glasses.” Among 20 observed individuals, 2 satisfy this attribute, while 18 do not belong to this category.
- The fourth observer focuses on “librarians without glasses.” Of the 5 observed individuals, 1 satisfies this condition, while 4 do not belong to this category.

Figure 8. Example of unequal sample sizes.

From Figure 8, it becomes clear that there are considerable differences in sample size between the individual observers. This leads to the result that the raw data, at the level of absolute frequencies, are no longer directly comparable.

In order to improve the comparability of the data as well as their visual representability, the raw values in the left representation are subjected to a standardization (normalization). (In the following, it will be explained why it is plausible to assume that a comparable procedure may also have been used in historical contexts.)

After this transformation, the structure shown in the right representation is obtained. The central significance of this step lies in the fact that, by eliminating differences in sample size, the structural relationships between the categories become comparable on a uniform scale. As a result, the underlying patterns of the data distribution can be more clearly identified.

Figure 9. Early-heaven Bagua together with He Tu and Luo Shu as potentially jointly used structures.

In an early historical phase, in which numerical notations, symbolic systems of expression, and even linguistic conventions had not yet been standardized, it can plausibly be assumed that people relied on readily available physical objects such as branches or stones to record, represent, and perform simple calculations with information.

In classical Chinese sources, the diagrams He Tu and Luo Shu frequently appear in close connection with the early-heaven Bagua diagram (cf. Fig. 9). Building on the previously developed interpretation of the Bagua as a structure for classification, statistical organization, and the representation of probabilistic relationships, the function of He Tu and Luo Shu can also be understood within a comparable structural framework.

Figure 10. Example of the application of He Tu and Luo Shu.

In Figure 10, the point-like markings (small stones) in the diagrams of He Tu and Luo Shu are distinguished by four different colors. It can be observed that the total number of points in each color group is 10. This suggests that the overall structure can be divided into four different combination forms, with each combination being based on the base number 10.

When using He Tu and Luo Shu, the small stones can only be moved within the regions defined by their respective colors. For example, in Figure 10 (top right), the ten stones marked in yellow can be transformed from a distribution of two stones at the top and eight at the bottom into another distribution, such as five at the top and five at the bottom.

In addition, a further possible interpretation is proposed: the centrally positioned point markings (small stones) in He Tu and Luo Shu may be understood as representing a value of “one half” ($1/2$). As shown in Figure 10 (bottom right), the presence of this special marking within a combination can be interpreted such that $1/2$ is subtracted from the base value; correspondingly, the other subset can be understood as an addition of $1/2$ to the base value.

Figure 11. Possible historical uses of the Bagua diagram.

In Figure 11, the use of Arabic numerals is omitted, and instead exclusively point-based representations (stones) are used. The resulting representation may be closer to the actual historical practices in which the Bagua was used for data processing and analysis.

Within this representational framework, the Bagua diagram can be interpreted as a structured tool for the representation and processing of data relationships. Through the binary division of fundamental elements and their combination across three levels, this structure integrates both the continuity of local changes and the systematic classification at a global level. In this way, a unified framework for the classification and analysis of data emerges.

6. Conclusion

The present study systematically analyzes, from a structural perspective, the construction of the Bagua diagram as well as its possible functions. The results show that the Bagua from the I Ching can be understood as a combinatorial structure consisting of three binary levels. Although it formally exhibits features reminiscent of the binary system developed by Leibniz, its internal structure should not be interpreted as a simple binary encoding, but rather as a system based on complement relations. In this respect, it shows a closer affinity to the fundamental concepts of set theory developed in 19th-century Europe, although the origins of the Bagua date back several thousand years.

At the structural level, it is shown that the early-heaven Bagua diagram occupies a unique position when a cyclic arrangement, symmetry constraints, the principle of minimal local change, and the condition of data analyzability comparable to that of the 2×2 contingency table are taken into account. Among the total of 5040 possible arrangements, this structure is not only one possible configuration but the only one that satisfies both the principle of minimal change and a structural correspondence to the 2×2 contingency table.

At the level of application, it is shown, based on a concrete example (the “Steve problem” formulated by Kahneman), that the Bagua structure is suitable for representing combined classification relationships. The analysis demonstrates that it enables the direct representation of comparative relationships between different categories within the same level while simultaneously preserving complement and symmetry mappings. A comparison with the 2×2 contingency table further shows that the two forms of representation emphasize different aspects: whereas the Bagua diagram highlights symmetric relationships and direct comparisons within a single level, the 2×2 contingency table is particularly suited to representing conditional dependencies between variables and proportional relationships. In essence, the Bagua corresponds in both structure and mode of operation to the 2×2 contingency table, without relying on percentage calculation, which had not yet been developed at that time.

Building on this, the representation of data under conditions of unequal sample sizes is examined. Through appropriate normalization, it is shown that the structure yields comparable results even with differing sample sizes and is therefore suitable not only for idealized but also for more realistic data situations. In connection with the structural analysis of He Tu and Luo Shu, it is proposed that these traditional diagrams may be interpreted as early forms of data representation. In a historical context lacking a unified symbolic system, point-based markings and their combinations may have served as a means for recording and analyzing data. The additional interpretation of certain markings as fractional values (e.g., $1/2$) further opens a possible extension toward a more refined representation of data relationships.

It should be emphasized that the interpretation proposed in this work is based primarily on structural considerations and that both the historical origins and the concrete modes of application of these diagrams require further investigation. Nevertheless, this interpretation appears plausible on the basis of currently available evidence: only two forms of the Bagua have been transmitted, of which the early-heaven Bagua examined here can be regarded as closer to the original form.

Future research may proceed in two directions: first, through a more rigorous mathematical formalization of the Bagua structure in order to determine its position more precisely within combinatorial or information-theoretical systems; second, through the investigation of possible applications in modern contexts, such as in the representation of probabilities, in cognitive decision-making processes, or in data classification. At the same time, further evidence or possible contradictions to the interpretation proposed here should be sought in historical sources.

In summary, this work proposes a structural approach to understanding the Bagua diagram, interpreting it as a potential framework for the representation and analysis of data. This perspective contributes to making the internal relationships of traditional diagrammatic forms visible and at the same time provides a new interpretative perspective as well as a directly applicable analytical approach to data analysis.

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